

PRACTISING WORDS THROUGH GAMES AND TASKS

Xurramova Shahriniso Qaxramon qizi

the 1st year BA student of Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8193350>

Abstract. *The article outlines practising words through classroom vocabulary games and exercises in Modern English language teaching methods. The main goals and objectives of the article are formulated. Based on the observation, the students' still have lack of vocabulary. The relevance of the issue under consideration is indicated. There are various teaching methods have been offered by the experts, one of them is through of word games and tasks. Word games are mostly used as it can appeal to young learners English. Therefore, this paper explores how word games can be used to practise students' vocabulary Mastery at primary school level. The study shows that one way to practise activity, creativity, imagination and group work skills along with academic achievement is to integrate fact and fiction, and a playful learning environment in teaching, studying and learning.*

Keywords: *word game, young learners, practical challenges, practical implication, game activities, word association, vocabulary pictionary, vocabulary hangman.*

Learning English is important for students in era globalization so we need to enhance English skill in the world community. To Master English students should begin learning English with vocabularies. The vocabulary is an important thing in learning English because without knowing vocabulary there is nothing we can express in four language skills, namely listening ,speaking, reading and writing.The students have to improve their Vocabulary Mastery, one of the strategy to improve student's vocabulary is by using game.[1] Game helps teachers to maximize each student's learning potential (S. Sugar & K 2002) Sanchez Morfin & Campos (Sanchez 2007) points that games give the student an opportunity to use their language in a less formal situation. So, the researcher chooses the game as learning strategy to improve student's vocabulary Mastery.[2] Game is very appropriate way to apply in teaching vocabulary. Game in classroom can be one of useful strategies in teaching. Games are fun activities to practise words. Games and tasks can promote interaction, thinking, learning and problem-solving strategies. In addition, Bonet (D1992) also explains that by a variety of odd words, puzzles and games can make learners motivate in learning vocabulary.[3]

“Games are effective tools for learning because they offer students a hypothetical environment in which they can explore alternative decisions without the risk of failure. Thought and action are combined into purposeful behavior to accomplish a goal. Playing games teach us how to strategize, to consider “alternatives and to think flexibly”’. [4] Games have a great educational value and it can be used in the classroom to make learners use the language instead of just thinking about learning the correct formulas. Games encourage learners to interact, cooperate to be creative in using the language in a meaningful way. Learners want to take part in activities; to play games and are generally ambitious. In order for them to take part, they must be able to understand and communicate in the target language. Games also encourage learners to keep interested in the work and a teacher can use them to create contexts in which the language is useful.[5] Learning vocabulary is one of the most important parts of English language.

Accordingly, teaching words with using games or different tasks help young pupils to understand words clearly and to memorize complicated words automatically in primary schools.

This paper is divided into four parts. The first part deals with a phenomenon of teaching English vocabulary to pupils among 6-10 years old. The second part discusses the importance of using games in practising vocabulary and what way using them is helpful. The third part investigates the practical implications of using games to teach vocabulary and some examples of games that could be used to teach words to young learners. The fourth part examines that teachers face some challenges when practising new words through using games.

2. Phenomenon of teaching English vocabulary.

2.1. Teaching young learners.

In the following section young learners will be defined and factors that might influence their maturity will be briefly mentioned[4]. Teaching English to young learners (TEYL) is a way to introduce English as a foreign language to young students. While children may not have an understanding of why it is important to learn a second language, there are many reasons that answer the question, “Why is English vocabulary important to teach pupils ?” For instance, creating a fun and positive learning environment can equip kids with a strong foundation for success in more advanced courses later in their academic careers.[6]

2.2. Who are young learners?

Young learners are agreed to be children from five or six years old who are in the first year of elementary schooling to twelve years old of age. However, the age of children is not necessarily indicator of how mature they are Philips (1993) stated that there are several factors influencing the maturity of children. These factors include their culture, environment (city or rural), and parents. Also, their development should be taken into consideration, some children develop very fast, and others might need more time. A good teacher of young learners should be aware of all their differences because understanding them can help teachers deciding on activities to be used in their teaching processes.[7]

3.The importance of using games in practising vocabulary and what way using them is helpful.

3.1 The significant of using games in practising words.

Games offer an environment where the learners can practise using new words and are free to express themselves. Multiple research studies show that participating in such activities can be an efficient way to develop communication skills, strengthen relationships and face the world with confidence. Games highly encourage and increase cooperation speechify, as an online English-speaking course in India, language game is one of the most important ways to practise effectively in a language class.[8] Games are really valuable and effective activities to teach words, grammar rules and English phonetics. Nowadays a lot of kids and English learners have some difficulties to memorize words, and to do different logical activities. That is way “What can we do to memorize words automatically?” In this section, Games are fantastic for learning at any age, so they are particularly important for young learners. Experts say that games are essential for healthy development in early childhood and beyond.

3.2. The practical implications of using games to teach new words and some exemplifications of games could be used to practise new words.

Play lets children practise what they know and also what they do not. It allows them to experiment through trial and error find solutions to problems, work out the best strategies, and

build new confidence and skills. In our busy live, it can be easy to forget the value of play. We often think play is not a good using of time and children should be doing some “proper” learning instead [9]. However, scientists and educators realize that we should pay attention play as serious learning. Through playing, children increase their thinking skills and abilities that help them to succeed in their future life, including in language learning. The balance of enjoyment and issue makes games such amazing tools for practising words. The purpose of these games is to strengthen vocabulary skills. These games are also known as “vocabulary games”, “letter games” and “vocabulary building games”. List of vocabulary games.

From Pictionary to word scrambles to synonym memory, here is a list of fun word games to play in classrooms, at home or during meetings:

1. VOCABULARY Pictionary

Pictionary is a game of charades where players draw words instead of acting them out. To play:

1. Split the group into teams.
2. Each round, assign one team member to draw.
3. Give the drawing team member a word.
4. Allow up to sixty seconds for teammates to guess.
5. If the team guesses correctly, then assign one point. The game is a great way to practise new words, as players connect the word with an image.

2. WORD ASSOCIATION.

Word Association is one of the best vocabulary games for kids and classrooms since playing does not require a large vocabulary. The rules are simple and easy to understand. Typically, the game involves in players. To play:

1. Player one says a word.
2. Player two responds with the first word that comes to mind.
3. Player one either chooses a new word or responds to player two’s word.
4. The game continues until one player repeats a word or pauses too long.

The rapid pace of the game generates excitement and occasionally results in funny answers. There are no wrong answers in word association, but the game can serve as a learning opportunity to find better words.

3. VOCABULARY HANGMAN.

Hangman is a classic chalkboard word game that translates easily to online play, thanks to digital whiteboards. To play:

1. Assign a player a word.
2. The player draws a series of blanks corresponding to the number of letters in the word.
3. Other players guess letters.
4. If the letter is in the word, then the “executioner” fills in the blank. If not, then the executioner draws one portion of the gallows.
5. The game ends when players guess the word, or when the picture is complete.[10]

The section examines that teachers face some problems when practising words using games and tasks.

Vocabulary teaching and learning is a continuous challenge for teachers and as well as students because generally there has been minimal focus on vocabulary teaching in the classrooms. Some institutions realize that using game is one of the methods that can help students when pupils

are engaged in playing with the other pupils. There are some disadvantages of fun game in learning new words. Sometimes game rules are too difficult and time consuming to practise words in a foreign language. So, students get tired and lost their energy over time when they find out that games do not correspond to their tasks and tests. In classroom some young learners especially teenagers may find games unnecessary and childish. They do not play games, as a result there have been many conflicts among children.

As a final point, when the students were interested in learning the material, they would give more attention to the lesson given. That condition gave a good chance for both the teacher and the students. On the time, the teacher could deliver the material very well and the students could understand what they had learnt on that day. The first disadvantage of applying games in teaching learning process was by attracting student's interest to games, all of them were active and made noisy. Sometimes they too much moved and spoke. That condition made the teacher difficult to control them.

To conclude, in this study I deal with practising words with games activities and game materials. Using an experimental method, this study realizes effectiveness of using word game, game activities, game materials on practising new words. During the expedition, I learnt that it is an important thing to learn about pupil characters and to get to know them. Because every learner's progress is different and we need to observe each person individually. They need to know good techniques and suitable material in order to gain the second language learning. Games create good learning conditions, so language learners would also prefer choosing games when practising new words since they are fun and no stress. Today, this theme is one of the most fascinating, disputable, and crucial issues of practising words.

REFERENCES

1. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338841996_IMPROVING_ENGLISH_VOCABULARY_MASTERY_THROUGH_WORD_GAME
2. S, Sugar & K, Sugar. 2002. "Primary Games: Experiential Learning Activities." Sanchez, Morfin & Campos. 2007. "Interactive Games In The Teaching Learning Process Of A Foreign Language."
3. D, Bonet. 1992. Vocabulary Improvement Words Made Easy.
4. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED617641.pdf>. Martinson and Chu 2008:478p
5. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED617641.pdf>
6. <https://www.tefl-online.com/tefl-jobs/online-tefl-articles/why-teach-english-young-learners/>
7. Phillips, S. (1993). Young learners. Oxford University Press: Oxford.
8. <https://speechify.in/blog/importance-of-language-games-in-learning-english>
9. <https://www.cambridgeenglish.org/learning-english/parents-and-children/your-childrens-interests/kids-are-here-to-play-the-importance-of-games>
10. <https://teambuilding.com/blog/vocabulary-games>